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Integration of BiOI nanosheets into bubble-propelled micromotors for efficient water purification

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ABSTRACT

Integration of 2D layered materials into micromotors is of great interest for scientists since 2D materials can endow micromotors with new characteristics or enhance their intrinsic properties. In this work, we develop the BiOI-based self-propelled micromotors (i.e., rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors) with tubular and arc geometric shapes via template-assisted electrochemical deposition method. BiOI, constructed by nanosheets, is a visible-light-excited photocatalyst. The elaborately designed heterostructure is able to promote the charge separation and transport capacity of BiOI. Each micromotor can not only exhibit vigorous stirring-like movement for self-propulsion but also lead to enhanced photocatalytic dynamics for dye degradation. Using Rhodamine 6G as the dye pollutant model, BiOI-based micromotors can degrade 94% of dye molecules within 30 min under visible light illumination while their degradation efficiency is only 5.2% when in dark. The dye degradation mechanism is mainly based on the generation of reactive oxygen species during the photocatalysis process. The synergistic effect among i) “on-the-fly” chemistry, ii) the collective behavior of micromotors and iii) the visible-light-excited BiOI photocatalyst with synthetic nanoflake morphology and well-designed heterojunction make an efficient and active photocatalytic platform for water purification.

Introduction

Contaminated water can endanger aquatic creatures and eventually jeopardize human health indirectly through the food chain. It is an emerging paradigm to utilize autonomous micromotors to actively remediate the polluted water source by removing or degrading pollutants in an “on-the-fly” fashion [1]. Various self-propelled micromotors driven by bubbles or light have been developed to remove or degrade contaminants, such as dyes [2], microplastics [3,4], heavy metals, oil [5], organic pollutants [6,7], pesticides [8], explosives [9], and even chemical warfare agents [10]. These “on-the-fly” micromotors can transform energy from their environment into autonomous movement and often show more efficient degradation of organic pollutants and microorganisms as compared to the stationary counterparts because of the enhanced mixing and mass transfer and effective contact probability in the water by vigorous movement.

Two-dimensional (2D) materials, such as graphene, graphene oxide (GO), reduced graphene oxide (rGO), MXenes, black phosphorus (BP), graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄), and BiOX (X = Cl, Br, I) are of great

interest for researchers due to their superior optical, electrical and other physical characteristics [11–14]. Integration of 2D materials with self-propelled or physical field-powered motors is the cutting edge of science and technology. For example, 3D-printed tubular graphene-based motors have been prepared by khezri et al [12]. The 3D-printed tubes were filled with aluminum/gallium molten alloy for autonomous propulsion and the outer surface of the tubes were covered with C₃N₄/chitosan hydrogel layer to provide the photocatalytic activity. The micromotors were able to efficiently degrade the molecular model for explosives (i.e., picric acid) under the illumination of visible light due to the photocatalytic capacity of C₃N₄ particles and the adsorption ability of chitosan hydrogel [12]. Degradation of nitroaromatic explosives was also fulfilled by using MXene-based micromotors with sandwich-like TiO₂@Ti₃C₂/Pt structures [15]. rGO/Pt tubular micromotors were reported to detect mycotoxins since the binding of free aptamers, capable of selective recognition of mycotoxins, to the graphene layer can result in the fluorescence quenching of the free-dye-labeled aptamers, providing an on-the-fly biosensing strategy [16]. Furthermore, mycotoxin analysis was conducted by using rGO/Ni/PtNPs micromotors [17].

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Tubular g-C₃N₄ micromotors can perform the stop-go response by turning on/off visible light sources and can remove heavy metals from contaminated water under simultaneous optical monitoring because of the intrinsic fluorescence and adsorptive properties of g-C₃N₄ [18]. More interestingly, the formation and migration of O₂ bubbles inside the g-C₃N₄ microtube can be visualized by optical microscopy due to the transparency of g-C₃N₄ materials.

Bismuth oxyiodide (BiOI), as a representative layered ternary material, is a visible-light-excited semiconductor photocatalyst. BiOI possesses a tetragonal matlockite crystal structure with the *P4/nmm* space group. As illustrated in Fig. 1a, the monolayer of BiOI is constructed from one [I-Bi-O-Bi-I] stacking, which is formed by one slab of [Bi₂O₂]²⁺ interleaved by double slabs of iodide ions [I]⁻. Due to its narrow bandgap (~1.8 eV) [19,20], BiOI has been widely reported as the visible-light-activated photocatalyst for the degradation of pollutants. However, its photocatalytic activity is limited due to (i) significant recombination of photogenerated electron-hole pairs, (ii) poor electrical conductivity, and (iii) slow hole transfer kinetics. Recently, many attempts have been made to address one or more of the above issues through controlling morphologies [21], forming heterojunctions, doping, or tuning the composition of BiOI. In this work, bubble-propelled rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors are synthesized via the template-assisted electrodeposition method. We adopt layered BiOI nanosheets as a robust light absorber, ZnO nanoparticles with an extremely high intrinsic electron mobility as electron transfer channel, transparent conductive rGO films as an electron acceptor, and cobalt phosphate (Co-Pi) as hole acceptor and catalytic site to enhance the light absorption, charge separation and transport, and surface chemical reactions (charge utilization). Pt nanoparticles enable the generation of plenty of bubbles by catalytic degradation of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), providing the driving force for the movement of the tubular micromotors. Rhodamine 6G is used as the model pollutant to evaluate the photocatalytic activities of on-the-fly micromotors, as demonstrated in Fig. 1b.

Experimental

Chemicals

Graphene oxide (GO) was synthesized by Tour method [22]. Zinc (II) chloride anhydrous (ZnCl₂), potassium chloride (KCl), bismuth (III) nitrate pentahydrate (Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O), potassium iodide (KI), p-benzoquinone, dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (K₂HPO₄), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄), cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate (Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O), sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%) and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were as analytical grade reagent obtained from LachNer, Czech Republic. commercially purchased. Chloroplatinic acid (H₂PtCl₆) was obtained from Safina, Czech Republic, and rhodamine 6G (Rh6G, C₂₈H₃₁N₂O₃Cl)

from Sigma Aldrich, Czech Republic. Unless otherwise specified, all reagents were used as received without further purification. The deionized water was adopted for all the experiments.

Synthesis of micromotors

The rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors were prepared via the template-assisted electrochemical deposition method using an Autolab PGSTAT204 (Eco Chemie, Utrecht, The Netherlands) controlled by NOVA Version 2.1.4 software. Commercially available polycarbonate (PC) membranes (Whatmann®) with an average pore diameter of 5 μm and length of 8 μm were used as the template. Prior to the electrodeposition, a layer of Au thin film with a thickness of 100 nm was deposited on the backside of the PC membrane by thermal vacuum deposition at a pressure of 1 × 10⁻⁵ mbar. Then the PC membrane was fixed to a holder, as shown in Figure S1. The membrane with Au layer was in contact with a copper plate and functioned as the conductive working electrode. Pt and Ag/AgCl were used as the counter electrode and reference electrode, respectively. The layer of rGO, ZnO, BiOI, Co-Pi, and Pt were sequentially electrodeposited on the PC membrane, referring to previous literature [23–27]. First of all, rGO was deposited on the inner surface of PC membrane by reducing graphene oxide via cyclic voltammetry (CV) technique in a 0.1 mg ml⁻¹ GO suspension containing 0.1 M H₂SO₄ and 0.5 M Na₂SO₄. Cycling potential was conducted from -1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) to +0.3 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) with a scan speed of 50 mV s⁻¹ for 5 scans. In the second step, ZnO layer was prepared under the chronoamperometry mode by applying a negative potential of -1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) for 5 min under the temperature of 80 °C in 5 mM ZnCl₂ aqueous solution containing 0.1 M KCl as supporting electrolyte. The electrolyte was purged with fresh air during the deposition process to supply enough oxygen for the generation of hydroxides. In the third step, BiOI layer was electrodeposited by applying a potential of -0.1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) for 5 min in an electrolyte (water:ethanol = 5:2) containing 0.03 M Bi(NO₃)₂, 0.3 M KI, and 0.067 M p-benzoquinone. Ethanol was added to increase the solubility of p-benzoquinone. In the fourth step, Co-Pi was synthesized at -1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) for 5 min in the 0.5 mM solution of Co(NO₃)₂ in 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH = 7). Finally, Pt layer was deposited at -0.1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) for 1 min from 0.01 M H₂PtCl₆ solution containing 0.01 M H₂SO₄ as the supporting electrolyte.

After the accomplishment of all electrodeposition procedures, the PC membrane was taken away from the holder. The gold layer on the backside of the membrane was gently removed by hand polishing with 15 μm alumina slurry. Subsequently, the membrane was placed in a 15 ml centrifuge tube. 10 ml dichloromethane was injected into the centrifuge tube and kept for 15 min to completely dissolve the membrane and thus release the micromotors. The micromotors were collected by centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 5 min and washed with ethanol and distilled water at 5000 rpm for 5 min, sequentially. All micromotors were stored in the distilled water at room temperature.

Characterization

The morphology of as-prepared micromotors was investigated by a Tescan Lyra 3 field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (FEG-SEM). To analyze the elemental composition, an energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analyzer from Oxford Instruments was used. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected by using a Bruker D8 Discoverer diffractometer. The acquired data were analyzed via HighScore Plus 3.0 software.

Motion record and track

Optical microscopy (Leica DM6000B) was used to visualize the motion behaviors of micromotors. To make a record of the motion videos, an HDMI USB Camera (1080P/60FPS, full HD) from Eakins,

Fig. 1. (a) Layered crystal structure of BiOI with stacked [I-Bi-O-Bi-I] drawn by VESTA software. (b) Schematic image of bubble-propelled BiOI-based micromotors for the photocatalytic degradation of pollutants in the contaminated water under the illumination of visible light. The composition of micromotors is demonstrated in the inset.

China was attached to the microscope. The trajectories and motion velocity of the micromotor were tracked and processed by using free-access Image J software.

Photocatalytic degradation

To investigate the photocatalytic degradation performance of rigorously moving micromotors, rhodamine 6G (Rh6G) was used as the model dye pollutant. For all the experiments, the initial concentration of Rh6G (0.01 mg/mL) and H_2O_2 (3 wt%) was kept the same. A blue laser (435 nm) with a current of 300 mA was adopted as the light source to illuminate the samples. The distance between the light source and a sample was maintained at 15 cm. The absorbance values at the maximum absorption wavelength of 526 nm, measured by UV-Vis spectroscopy, were used for calculating the photodegradation efficiency. The definition of dye degradation efficiency is shown as below:

$$\text{Degradation efficiency} = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where C is the concentration of Rh6G after being degraded for a specific period (t); C_0 is the initial concentration of Rh6G. Since the concentration of Rh6G is linearly proportional to the absorption value, the degradation efficiency can be calculated based on the absorbance values:

$$\text{Degradation efficiency} = \frac{\text{Abs}(t_0) - \text{Abs}(t)}{\text{Abs}(t_0)} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Results and discussion

Morphology and structure of micromotors

The rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors were fabricated by the electrochemical method using PC membrane as a template. Optical microscopy can provide rough geometrical shape information of the prepared micromotors. As shown in Fig. S2, some micromotors preserved intact tubular structure while some were fractured, resulting in the formation of arc structure. The tubular geometry was shaped by the intrinsic micropore structure of the PC membrane. The fracture of the tube may be caused by the strong centrifugation force during the centrifugation procedure. Fig. 2a demonstrates the SEM image of a typical tubular micromotor. The length of this micromotor is around 10 μm . From the cross-sectional image in Fig. 2b, flower-like structures in the inner wall of the tube can be observed. Such a 3D flower-like structure was constructed by the self-assembly of extremely thin 2D plate-like crystals of BiOI [25]. The randomly oriented nanoflakes with variable gaps among them endowed the micromotors with high surface area, which is beneficial to photocatalytic reactions due to the presence of much more catalytic active sites. Besides, the network of the ultra-thin BiOI nanoflakes has been reported to possess high electron-hole separation efficiency [28,25]. The successful synthesis of BiOI was further confirmed by the existence of tetragonal phase BiOI in XRD patterns (Fig. S3). To further validate the existence of these materials, element mapping by EDX was conducted. As shown in Fig. 2c, the elements C, Zn, Bi, O, I, Co, and Pt were detected and uniformly distributed within the whole body of the microtube, indicating the successful fabrication of rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors.

Movement of micromotors

The motion behavior of micromotors was captured by the camera attached to the optical microscope. The representative movement trajectory of a tubular micromotor and an arc micromotor was shown in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b (Video S1 and Video S2), respectively. The autonomous movement of micromotors was driven by O_2 bubbles which were generated from the H_2O_2 decomposition on Pt layer (i.

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image of rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors. (b) Cross-sectional image of micromotors and corresponding (c) elemental composition from EDX analysis.

Fig. 3. Time-lapse microscope images of (a) a tubular micromotor and (b) an arc micromotor moving in 5% H_2O_2 and 0.125 wt% SDS. The tracked trajectories of micromotors were highlighted in blue. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

e., $2H_2O_2 \xrightarrow{Pt} 2H_2O + O_2$). The O_2 bubbles induced the stirring movement of the two micromotors. The tubular micromotor exhibited a larger average velocity ($63.1 \mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) when compared with arc micromotor ($10.4 \mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). However, more bubbles were found around the arc micromotor because of the larger exposure area of Pt layer to the H_2O_2 solution. Different from our common sense, these bubbles did not promote the forward motion of the arc, but somehow generated a drag force to impede the proceeding of the micromotor. The speed of bubble-propelled micromotors is controlled mainly by two opposite forces. The force from the fuel decomposition in the catalytic layer propels the advance of micromotors while the force from the rough surface of micromotors with the fluid impedes their forwarding movement.

Swarm of micromotors and dye degradation

The efficiency of single micromotors for executing a specific task (e. g., removal of pollutant molecules, delivery of therapeutic drugs, killing of cancer cells) is limited. In practical application, plenty of micromotors

are required to collaboratively fight against environmental or biomedical threats or to complete a designated task. Such collaboration behavior is called “collective behavior” or “swarm”, which is inspired by many phenomena in nature such as flocking of birds or teamwork behaviors of insects [29]. The swarm of bubble-propelled micromotors was demonstrated in Fig. 4a (Video S3). All the micromotors rigorously moved along their respective trajectories. The motion mode and velocity were morphology-dependent.

To evaluate the on-the-fly chemistry of micromotors with BiOI-based heterostructure, the photocatalytic degradation of Rh6G model dye was performed. As shown in Fig. 4b, within 60 min, almost 94% of dye molecules were successfully degraded by the BiOI-based micromotors under the irradiation of visible light. Effective organic pollutant removal can be ascribed to three main reasons. First, H_2O_2 contributed to dye degradation. This inference is confirmed by the result from a control experiment that the degradation efficiency was 22.5% when the Rh6G dye molecules were put in the hydrogen peroxide solution (3% H_2O_2) in the absence of micromotors under the same visible light irradiation condition. Similar to hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and superoxide anion ($\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$), H_2O_2 belongs to reactive oxygen species (ROS). The effect of ROS on organic pollutant degradation has been widely reported [30,31]. Second, vigorous stirring-like movement from the “on-the-fly” micromotors provides higher surface contact probability between the active particles and contaminations, thereby leading to accelerated dynamics of pollutant entrapping or degradation. To confirm the stirring effect on the pollutant degradation, Rh6G dye was placed in H_2O_2 solution under the condition of blue light illumination and continuous stirring (500 rpm) via a stirring bar. After photocatalytic reaction for 60 min, the degradation efficiency of dye was 39.7%, which was higher than that without external stirring movement (22.5%). Besides, the “Rh6G- H_2O_2 (light + stirring)” group exhibited a better contamination degradation performance than “Rh6G- H_2O_2 (light)” at each time interval, indicating the vigorous movement can boost the photocatalytic reaction dynamics via increasing the contact areas between the pollutant molecules and H_2O_2 . Such stirring effect was fulfilled in bubble-propelled micromotors via vigorous autonomous movement. The third reason is that BiOI, as a visible-light-excited photocatalyst, was constructed with plenty of 2D BiOI nanosheets. The high specific surface area of 2D materials provides more catalytic active sites for dye degradation activities. Besides, the deliberately designed heterostructure could facilitate an effective electron-hole separation of BiOI nanosheets, thus resulting in enhanced catalytic reactions. As a comparison, 79% of dye can be degraded by the BiOI/Pt micromotors after visible light illumination for one hour. The increase of degradation efficiency from 79% (BiOI/Pt micromotors) to 94% (rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi/Pt micromotors) confirmed the positive

effect of heterostructure on the photocatalytic ability. The degradation mechanism of BiOI-based photocatalyst is also based on the generation of ROS, which will be discussed later. In contrast, in the absence of light radiation, only 5.2% of the dye pollutants were degraded by micromotors within 60 min since no photocatalysis can proceed without light. Similarly, the degradation efficiency was only 1.8% when Rh6G dye was stored in an H_2O_2 solution in dark. In conclusion, the synergistic effect among photocatalysis of BiOI-based heterostructure, ROS influence, and “on-the-fly” chemistry of micromotors facilitated the effective elimination of organic contaminants for wastewater purification.

Photocatalytic degradation mechanism of BiOI-based heterojunction

Here, we will discuss the possible mechanism of photocatalytic degradation of dyes. Since the bandgap of BiOI is around 1.8 eV [20], BiOI is capable of absorbing photons when illuminated by light with a wavelength smaller than 688 nm. Electrons in the valence band (VB) of the activated BiOI will jump into the conductive band (CB), leaving holes in the VB (demonstrated in Eq. (3)). Ideally, the photoexcited charge carriers (i.e., electrons and holes) can smoothly migrate to the surface and participate in the chemical reaction for dye degradation. However, electrons and holes tend to recombine in the bulk, at the material/solution interface, and even at defect sites (e.g., boundary). Hence, we designed a heterostructure to decrease the recombination probability of electrons and holes and help charge carriers to smoothly arrive at the sites of reactants. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the activated electrons in the CB of BiOI will first be transferred to ZnO due to the presence of ZnO/BiOI p-n heterojunction [20], and then electrons will be transferred to the material/solution interface using rGO as a channel for the generation of superoxide anions ($\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$) (Eq. (4)). The role of graphene in boosting electron transfer has been reported by many researchers [32–34]. The holes in the CB of BiOI nanoflakes will be transferred to Co-Pi. Co-Pi layer, which is widely used as an oxygen evolution reaction (OER) co-catalyst [35,36], can efficiently capture photogenerated holes at the material/solution interface. Hence, Co-Pi will be first be oxidized to Co(III) species and then be further oxidized to Co(IV) species due to the continuous hole injection from BiOI nanosheets. As a result, the highly active Co(IV) species can efficiently oxidize water and hydroxyl to produce hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) (Eq. 5–6). The reactive oxygen species including generated “free radicals” ($\cdot\text{OH}$ and $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$) and H_2O_2 in the solution is responsible for the oxidation of organic pollutants, leading to the formation of carbon dioxide (CO_2) and byproducts [37], as demonstrated in Eq. (7). Many researchers have adopted measurement methods such as electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR), electron spin resonance (ESR), and so on [38–41] to prove that ROS is the culprit for the mineralization of dye pollutants during the photocatalytic reaction process.

Fig. 4. (a) Swarm of micromotors. The micromotors were highlighted via blue dashed circles. (b) Degradation of model dye (i.e., Rhodamine 6G). Initial dye concentration (0.01 mg/mL), H_2O_2 concentration (3 wt%), the wavelength of the light source (435 nm), applied current (300 mA), and distance between the sample and light source (15 cm) maintained the same for all the research groups. For the group which required the external stirring movement, a stirring bar is used and the stirring speed was kept at 500 rpm. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Schematic of the energy band structure of rGO/ZnO/BiOI/Co-Pi heterojunction and photocatalytic mechanism of dye degradation.

An ideal photocatalyst is supposed to exhibit strong light-harvesting, fast charge separation and transfer, and efficient surface chemical reaction. To meet such requirements, various heterojunction architectures with optimized energy band diagrams have been designed [42–44]. Morphology also plays a key role in photocatalytic performance for pollutant degradation [45,46]. In this work, visible-light-excited layered BiOI photocatalyst with nanosheet morphology and elaborately designed heterostructure accounts for high dye removal efficiency of micromotors from the perspective of material science.

Conclusions

BiOI-based self-propelled micromotors were developed by sequentially electrically-depositing rGO, ZnO, BiOI, Co-Pi, and Pt layers in the inner wall of the PC membrane pore prior to the chemical dissolving of membrane for the release of micromotors. This template-assisted electrochemical deposition method resulted in the formation of micromotors with mainly two geometrical shapes: tubular structure and arc structure. The average velocity of tubular micromotor in 3% H₂O₂ solution was almost six times larger than that of arc structure. The assembly of the bubble-propelled micromotors, stirring vigorously in their respective local areas, could lead to the collective behavior of micromotors, which is suitable for executing complex, time-consuming, or massive tasks. As a proof of concept, the task of dye degradation was delivered to the BiOI-based photocatalytic micromotors. Within half an hour, 94% of dye pollutants were degraded by the autonomous micromotors under visible light irradiation. The significant pollutant degradation efficiency was mainly attributed to the synergy effect of the visible-light-excited photocatalyst of BiOI with 2D nanosheets, deliberately designed heterojunction for effective electron-hole separation, and vigorous stirring movement of bubble-propelled micromotors. This work sheds new light on the integration of 2D materials into on-the-fly micromotors for environmental remediation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Huaijuan Zhou: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Bing Wu:** Investigation. **Lukas Dekanovsky:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Shuangying Wei:** Investigation. **Bahareh Khezri:** Writing – original draft. **Tomas Hartman:** Investigation. **Jinhua Li:** Investigation. **Zdenek Sofer:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flatc.2021.100294>.

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